

PROGRAMMING REALIZATION OF PERMUTATIONS¹

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Abstract. *We are studying permutations. Algorithms for generating permutations are shown: a naive one, and an algorithm based on the successor of a given permutation. Both algorithms are realized in C++. The second part of this work shows rank and unrank functions for permutation.*

Keywords: *permutation, rank function, unrank function, parallel execution.*

In Mathematics, and combinatorial mathematics in particular, there are many topics that can serve the computer science and STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) students in general. Being a part of the larger subject – discrete mathematics, Combinatorics is, in large part briefly mentioned and seemingly “simple”, in fact is posing some challenges when programming the needed algorithms. The main goal of this research is to introduce the reader to two topics: permutations and Latin squares. The structure of this note is as follows: We begin with an introduction in Section I, then, in Section II we review the mainstream recursive algorithm for generating permutations and the iterative algorithm. Section III is dedicated to the **rank** and **unrank** functions which can be used for constructing objects or to find the next object in the family. In this work we show mathematical formulae that can be used to realize such **rank** and **unrank** functions for permutations. Since we can start from a random point in the ordered set of all $n!$ permutations we can implement an algorithm that easily can be modified for parallel execution enabling the benefits of the modern multi-core central processing units.

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I. Introduction

Let $\Omega = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ be a set of n objects. The *symmetric group* S_Ω on the set Ω is the group of all permutations of the objects in the set. Since the permutations does not depend on the objects themselves, usually, the symmetric group is denoted by S_n , and is known as the symmetric group of degree n . It is well known that the number of permutations is $|S_n| = 1 \cdot 2 \dots n = n!$ (see [1]).

The set S_n of all permutation is lexicographically ordered and we say that a permutation π is *lexicographically smaller* than σ (we denote it by $\pi < \sigma$) if and only if for the smallest $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ with $\pi_i \neq \sigma_i$ we have $\pi_i < \sigma_i$. A permutation $\tau \in S_n$ is the *successor* of $\pi \in S_n$ if there is no permutation $\sigma \in S_n, \sigma \neq \tau$ such that $\pi < \sigma < \tau$.

II. Permutations

Almost all the introductory books in programming for undergraduates and colleges when introducing the symmetric group generate it with the following recursive Algorithm 1.

For example, running Algorithm 1 for the set $\Omega = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ can be done with the following code:

```
char str[] = "abcdef";  
permute(str, 0, n);
```

We have uploaded a C++ realization of this algorithm in [6]. Unfortunately, the above algorithm does not perform well for large n , e.g. $n \geq 14$ since almost always the sheer number of permutations is so huge that the algorithm does not finishes.

Other algorithms for generating permutations exist, for example Heap's algorithm (see [2]), in which all possible permutations of a set of objects is obtained, in such a way that each permutation differs from its predecessor only by the interchange of two of the objects.

```

#include <iostream>
#include <string.h>
using namespace std;
void permute(char a[], int i, int n)
{
    int j;
    if(i == n) // If we've chosen all
        cout << a << endl; // we're done, output
    else
    {
        for (j = i; j <= n; j++) // a[0] to a[j-1] are done
        { // so try all possible a[j]
            swap(a[i], a[j]); // Choose a[j] or a[n]
            permute(a, i+1, n); // Choose the remaining letter
            swap(a[i], a[j]);}
        }
    }
}
void swap(char *x, char *y)
{
    char temp;
    temp = *x;
    *x = *y;
    *y = temp;}
int main(){
    char str[] = "ABCD";
    int n = strlen(str);
    permute(str, 0, n-1);
    return 0;}

```

Algorithm 1: Recursive generation of S_n

It is more interesting in the modern age to consider algorithms suited for parallel execution so that it is easier to use nowadays on multi-core CPUs and on multithreads GPUs. Thus, we present the following algorithm (see [1, Algorithm 3.12.4], [3, ex. 1-26, 1-33]) which we discuss mathematically and was realized in C++.

The following algorithm finds the successor permutation σ to the permutation $\pi = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_n)$:

1. Search for the largest index r with $\pi_r < \pi_{r+1}$. If no such r exists, then $\pi = (n, n-1, \dots, 1)$ is the last permutation.
2. Search for the index $s > r$ with $\pi_s > \pi_r > \pi_{s+1}$.
3. Then the successor permutation is the following:
 - (1) $\sigma = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_{r-1}, \pi_n, \dots, \pi_{s+1}, \pi_r, \pi_{s-1}, \dots, \pi_{r+1})$.

This algorithm can be implemented as shown in Algorithm 2. For simplicity this algorithm prints the next permutation, or it prints "last" if the next permutation does not exist. The correctness of this algorithm can be checked in [7].

```

#include <iostream>
using namespace std;
int main()
{
    int n = 6; // the size of the array
    int pi [n] = {1, 2, 5, 3, 4, 6}; // the current perm.
    int r=n-1;
    int k=0;
    int nx[n]; // next perm.
    while((pi[r]<pi[r-1])&&(r>0)){r--;} // finding r
    int s=0;
    if(r==0){cout <<"last"<< endl;} // there is no next
    else{ // perm. implement eq. (1)
        s = r;
        while((s<n) && (pi[s-1]>pi[r-1]) && (pi[r-1]>pi[s])){s++;}
        for(int i=0;i<r-1;i++){nx[k] = pi[i];k++;}
        for(int i=n-1;i>s;i--){nx[k] = pi[i];k++;}
        nx[k]=pi[r];k++;
        for(int i=s-1;i>=r-1;i--){nx[k] = pi[i];k++;}
        for(int t=0;t<n;t++){cout << nx[t];}
        return 0;}

```

Algorithm 2: Generating the successor of a permutation

III. Rank and unrank functions for permutations

A *ranking algorithm* determines the position (or rank) of a combinatorial object among all the objects (with respect to a given order). Suppose that S with n elements. A *ranking function* will be a bijection $\mathbf{rank}: S \rightarrow \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. A rank function defines a total ordering on the elements of S , by the obvious rule $s < t \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{rank}(s) < \mathbf{rank}(t)$.

An unranking algorithm finds the object having a specified rank. Thus, ranking and unranking can be considered as inverse operations. There is a unique rank function associated with any total ordering defined on S . This function unrank is also a bijection $\mathbf{unrank}: \{0, \dots, n-1\} \rightarrow S$ with the property $\mathbf{rank}(s) = i \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{unrank}(i) = s, \forall s \in S, 0 \leq i < n-1$.

Good and fast ranking and unranking algorithms play important role in combinatorial calculations. For example, if we need to generate a random element from the set of objects S we only need to generate a random integer $i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$ and use **unrank**(i). Another common use of the pair **rank/unrank** is when we need to store combinatorial objects in the memory, we simply store the **rank** of the element, which is an integer, and if we need the combinatorial object we just **unrank** it.

Given a ranking function, **rank**, defined on S , the successor function, which we name **successor**, satisfies the following rule **successor**(s) = $t \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{rank}(t) = \mathbf{rank}(s) + 1$.

Thus, **successor**(s) is the next element following s in the total ordering. We will use the convention that **successor**(s) is undefined if **rank**(s) = $n-1$ (i.e., if s is the last (largest) element in S). The function **successor** can easily be constructed from the functions **rank** and **unrank**, according to the following formula:

$$\mathbf{successor}(s) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{unrank}(\mathbf{rank}(s) + 1) & \text{if } \mathbf{rank}(s) < n-1, \\ \text{undefined} & \text{if } \mathbf{rank}(s) = n-1. \end{cases}$$

When we have constructed the successor function, it is a simple matter to generate all the elements in S . We would do this by beginning with the first element of S and applying the function **successor** $n-1$ times.

As we are about to see the above construction is very useful when we are dealing with permutations. Let n be an integer number and we want to construct the symmetric group S_n . Since $|S_n| = n!$ we have **rank** : $S_n \rightarrow \{0, \dots, n!-1\}$ and its reverse function **unrank** : $\{0, \dots, n!-1\} \rightarrow S_n$. As we have already established the successor function for the set of permutations S_n we simple need to define and implement **rank** and **unrank** functions and we are done.

A computer program that realize such functions for permutation will use the minimum needed RAM for calculating all permutations or a subset of permutations.

We assign the number 0 to the smallest permutation $(1, 2, \dots, n)$. We assign 1 to the next permutation, and so on, giving the last permutation $(n, n-1, \dots, 1)$ the number $n! - 1$. The problem is to determine the number **rank** $(\pi) = l_n(\pi)$ assigned to a given permutation $\pi = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_n)$. Let us define the function l_n such that

$$(2) \quad l_1(1) = 0, \quad l_n(\pi) = (\pi_1 - 1)(n-1)! + l_{n-1}(\pi'),$$

where $\pi' = (\pi'_1, \dots, \pi'_{n-1})$ is derived from π by deleting π_1 and reducing all $\pi_j > \pi_1$ by 1. For example:

$$l_4(3214) = 2.3! + l_3(213) = 2.3! + 2! + l_2(12) = 2.3! + 2! = 14.$$

The implementation of (2) in C++ is given in Algorithm 3, also available in [8].

```

#include <iostream>
#include <string.h>
using namespace std;
const int n = 4;
int pi[n]; int pi_prime[n]; int j;
int main() {
    int r=0;
    pi[1]=3; pi[2]=2; pi[3]=1; pi[4]=4;
    for(int i=1; i<n+1; ++i) pi_prime[i]=pi[i];
    for(j=1; j<n; ++j) {
        int fact = 1;
        for(int k=2; k<(n-j+1); ++k) fact = fact*k;
        r=r+(pi_prime[j]-1)*fact;
        for(int i=j+1; i<n+1; ++i)
            if(pi_prime[i]>pi_prime[j]) pi_prime[i]=pi_prime[i]-1;
    }
    cout << r << endl;
    return 0; }

```

Algorithm 3: Finding rank for a given permutation

In order to define the **unrank** function we can use the factorial representation of a given permutation $\pi = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_n)$. Let $0 \leq r = \mathbf{rank}(\pi) \leq n! - 1$ is the rank of the permutation. Define

$$(3) \quad r = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} d_k \cdot k!,$$

where $0 \leq d_k \leq k$. Then the factorial representation of the permutation π is $(d_{n-1}, d_{n-2}, \dots, d_1, 0)$. From the factorial representation $(d_{n-1}, d_{n-2}, \dots, d_1, 0)$ we can reconstruct the permutation $\pi = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_n)$ by using the reverse function of $l_n(\pi)$ defined by (2):

We have $\pi_1 = d_{n-1} + 1$ because exactly d_{n-1} blocks of size $(n-1)!$ come before π . Then, the rest of the permutation $\pi_2, \pi_3, \dots, \pi_n$ is computed from permutation π' as follows:
 $\pi' = \mathbf{unrank}(r', n-1)$,

$$(4) \quad r' = r - d_{n-1} \cdot (n-1)!$$

$$(5) \quad \pi_i = \begin{cases} \pi'_{i-1} & , \text{ if } \pi'_{i-1} < \pi_i \\ \pi'_{i-1} + 1 & , \text{ if } \pi'_{i-1} > \pi_i \end{cases} \quad \text{for } 2 \leq i \leq n.$$

For example, we use Algorithm 4 (obtained from (4) and (5)) in C++ for finding the $\mathbf{unrank}(r)$, where in this instance we have chosen $r=110$. This code is also available in [8].

```

#include <iostream>
#include <string.h>
using namespace std;
const int n = 5;
int pi[n];
int main()
{int r=110; // chose the value
pi[n]=1;
int fact=1; // we use var. to calculate j! recursively
for(int j=1;j<n;++j)
{fact=fact*j;
int d=(r%(fact*(j+1)))/fact; // equation (4)
r=r-d*fact;
pi[n-j]=d+1;
for(int i=n-j+1;i<n+1;++i)
if((pi[i]>d)){pi[i]=pi[i]+1;}} // equation (5)
for(int i=1;i<n+1;++i) (cout << pi[i]);}
return 0;}

```

Algorithm 4: Finding unrank for a given value r

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